

Disrespect and Abuse during Childbirth : Exploring the Experiences, Prevalence, and Patterns Among Recently Delivered Women

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ABSTRACT

Background: Disrespect and abuse (DAA) during childbirth in a health facility are significant concerns as they affect the quality of maternal healthcare and violate women's rights. **Objective:** To document the experiences, prevalence, and pattern of DAA among newly delivered mothers attending the immunisation clinic. **Methodology:** This quantitative, prospective cross-sectional study involved 382 women who had recently given birth within the last six weeks and came to have their babies immunized. The participants were selected through a purposive consecutive sampling method, and data were gathered via a pretested questionnaire that explored their sociodemographic details and childbirth experiences. Data analysis was done to document prevalence, associations, and statistical significance. Analysis was conducted with IBM SPSS version 25. **Results:** Of the 382 participants, 92 (24.1%) reported suffering one or more forms of abuse during childbirth. Factors significantly associated with DAA during childbirth are identifying as a Christian ($P = 0.025$), not utilizing antenatal care ($P = 0.033$), having fewer antenatal care visits ($P = 0.027$), and giving birth at night ($P = 0.001$). The most common forms of DAA suffered were multiple forms of abuse 50 (13.1%), non-dignified care 22 (5.8%), non-consented care 14 (3.7%), and physical abuse 10 (2.6%). Overall, 326 (85.3%) of the participants expressed their satisfaction with the delivery process. **Conclusion:** DAA remains a significant concern that undermines maternal health and violates women's rights. Addressing these issues requires a multifaceted approach involving policy reform, healthcare provider education, and increased investment in maternal health infrastructure.

Keywords: Healthcare disparities, Maternal health services, Patient's satisfaction, Respect, Women's health.

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INTRODUCTION

Maternal mortality remains high in sub-Saharan Africa, and Nigeria in particular, with its large population and high fertility rate, continues to contribute a significant proportion of world maternal mortality. In 2015, the World Health Organization (WHO) estimated that 19% of global maternal deaths occurred in Nigeria with an estimated maternal mortality ratio (MMR) of 814 per 100,000 live births, and this placed a lifetime risk of maternal death at 1 in 22 in contrast to 1 in 4900 in developed countries.¹ Trained birth attendants at delivery has been shown to reduce maternal mortality, unfortunately, it has also been estimated that 58.6% of deliveries in Nigeria do not occur in Health facilities.² There is growing evidence suggesting that women prefer to deliver in the hands of traditional birth attendants.³ Some of the reasons given by pregnant women for choosing traditional birth attendants (TBAs) over skilled birth attendants (SBAs) included poor attitude of and abuse by health workers, the belief in the effectiveness of traditional remedies, longstanding cultural customs, more convenient access to TBAs and the higher expense of services at formal health facilities.^{3,4} Azuh *et al.* in Ota, Ogun State, South-Western Nigeria, reported that several women believe that delivering in a noninstitutional setting is better than in a modern facility because traditional birth attendants show more concern and compassion than skilled birth attendants.⁵ Similarly, Idris *et al.* in Giwa Local Government Area (LGA) of Kaduna State Nigeria, reported that despite living close to a health facility with free maternal health services, the majority of the women were not utilizing the facility for child delivery.⁶ One of the reasons for the poor use of the formal health system in that community is the belief that healthcare providers have a negative attitude; consequently, many women would rather give birth at home or at a traditional health centre.⁶

Increasing concern and evidence suggest that disrespect and abuse during childbirth in healthcare facilities are widespread globally, posing a significant obstacle to achieving positive maternal health outcomes.^{7,8,9} DAA has been defined as “any form of inhumane treatment or uncaring behavior toward a woman during labour and delivery”.^{10,11} It is found among all socio-economic groups, but it seems to be more common in developing countries, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia.¹² Disrespectful treatment may be due to absent or inadequate national human rights policies and their enforcement, lack of leadership in the health system, poor standards of care in facilities, provider demoralization, and shortages.⁹ DAA during childbirth can occur in various forms such as being shouted at, ignored, slapped by healthcare providers, and abandoned to deliver a child alone in health facilities.^{8,13,14} Different attempts have been made to define and categorize this topic. In a 2010 landscape analysis, Bowser and Hill⁹ described seven categories of disrespectful and abusive care during childbirth – physical abuse, nonconsensual care, non-confidential care, undignified care, discrimination, abandonment of care, and detention in facilities.

Women experiencing DAA during childbirth may not choose the facility for subsequent deliveries and may not recommend it to other women.¹⁵ DAA during childbirth not only affects healthcare utilization and maternal mortality but also is a violation of the basic human rights of females.¹⁶ In 2014, acknowledging the rise of this public health issue, the WHO strengthened its guidance to prevent and eliminate DAA during childbirth. It issued new recommendations aimed at enhancing intrapartum care for a more positive birth experience and collaborated with UNAIDS to establish an agenda striving for zero discrimination in healthcare settings.^{17,18}

Despite the recommendations, the rate of DAA remains high with wide variations reported in many regions of Nigeria. Ijadunol *et al.*¹⁹ and Naiyeju *et al.*²⁰ in South-West Nigeria reported rates of 19% and 82% respectively. Nwafor *et al.*²¹ reported a rate of 47.6% in South-East Nigeria while Iruo *et al.*²² reported a rate of 26.7% in South-South Nigeria. Despite the importance of DAA, there has not been any documented review in our locality/hospital. Central Hospital Agbor where this study was conducted is a secondary health facility in Delta State. In November 2007, the Delta State Government launched a free maternal health program covering costs for antenatal care, delivery (including Caesarean section), postpartum, postnatal care, medications, lab tests, surgical management of ectopic pregnancy, and blood transfusions. The program, maintained by successive governments, aims to minimize finance-related healthcare issues.

The objective of this study therefore was to assess the prevalence, patterns, and contributing factors of DAA experienced among delivered women presenting at the immunization clinic of Central Hospital Agbor. It is anticipated that the insights gained from this research will inform the creation of policy briefs, assisting policymakers and program officers across various governmental levels in devising effective interventions to address and prevent the issue of DAA during childbirth.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area: Central Hospital Agbor was established in the year 1906. It is a 250-bed hospital located in the South-South region of Nigeria. It provides general medical care and specialist services to indigenes of Delta State and neighboring parts of Edo State. The people of Agbor town are Ika, and they speak the Ika dialect of the Igbo language. Agbor has a population of about 67,000 people who are predominantly Christians of different denominations. Some of the indigenes practice African traditional religion, and

there are a few migrant Hausa/Fulani Muslims. The main occupational activities of the indigenes of Agbor town are farming and trading.

Study Design: This was a quantitative cross-sectional study conducted at the immunisation clinic of Central Hospital Agbor, Delta State, Nigeria, between February 1st, 2024 to 30th, 2024.

Study Population /Inclusion and Exclusion

Criteria: All women who delivered in the last six Weeks and attended the immunization clinic during the study period were eligible to participate after providing informed consent.

Women who delivered at home or in a traditional birth attendant place were excluded.

Women who had Caesarean sections were excluded.

Data collection: The questionnaire was developed with some modifications from a previous study by Naiyeju *et al.*²⁰ The specific questions utilized in the study were initially tested with a small, random sample of 30 potential respondents who were not part of the main study. This was done to verify the suitability of the included items. Overall, the items demonstrated strong internal consistency, suggesting that the instrument was reliable and valid. Three clinic staff were trained to help with the questionnaire administration. The objectives of the study were explained to the women who met the inclusion criteria, and informed consent was obtained from them. A total of 382 women who presented at the immunisation clinic and consented to participate in the study were recruited between 1st February 2024 and 30th June 2024 using a purposive consecutive sampling technique. The clinic staff ticked the corresponding answer on the questionnaire that the respondents answered. This method helped to ensure correct answers were entered, and it also helped to reduce the attrition rate. The socio-demographic characteristics, experience

regarding DAA, and types of DAA experienced were documented.

Categorization of Type of Abuse: Using the Bowser and Hills categorization of DAA, participants were asked specific questions on what they considered abuse. They were assigned to the type of DAA based on their responses.

Physical Abuse: Hitting, (slapped, beaten), forcing legs apart, tied down during labour

Non-dignified care: Threat to stop treatment, blame if outcome is poor, seen as a lazy person

Non-consented care: non-consented episiotomy, forceful and non-consented vaginal examination

Non-confidential care: No privacy, no screen or cover during vaginal examination, disclosure of medical history or exam

Neglect/abandonment: Delivering without the birth attendant present, ignored when help was needed, delivering outside the delivery room

Detention: Detention due to failure to pay, or not showing gratification

Discrimination: Denial of treatment or maltreatment based on residence, age, marital status, education, or occupation

Sample Size Calculation: The study sample size of 380 was derived based on the formula: $N = Z^2pq/e^2$, where N =minimum required sample size, Z =standard variate (1.96), P =estimated prevalence of DAA of 54.5% from the study by Kalu *et al.*,²³ $q=(1-p)$, e^2 =acceptable error at 0.05. $N = (1.96)^2 (0.55) (0.45) / (0.05)^2 = 380$. However, 382 participants who presented within the period were recruited.

Ethical Clearance: The study protocol was approved by the hospital's Ethical Committee

with ethical no. E/Com.AMZ/02/24. Recruitment of study participants was voluntary based on verbal briefing in English, pidgin English, or the local languages as appropriate. The study was executed under the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki, 2013. The authors are available and ready to supply the data on request.

Data Analysis: The data generated were analyzed using the IBM Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 25. Variables were presented with descriptive statistics using frequencies, percentages, and averages in means (standard deviation) and presented as tables. Tests of significance of differences were done at p values <0.05 using the Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test, where appropriate for categorical variables.

RESULTS

Of the 400 patients approached to join the study, 391 completed questionnaires that were available for analysis. Of the 391 returned questionnaires, 382 had complete information, and these were included in the final analysis. The mean age of participants was 28.8 ± 5.3 years, with a minimum and maximum ages of 17 and 45 years. Most participants were between 21-30 and 31-40 years, making up 59.3% and 32.4% respectively. The participants were predominantly Christians, 342 (89.5%), while only 14 (3.7%) were Muslims. Ika indigenes were 170 (44.5%) while Ibos and the other tribes made up 84 (22.0%) and 128 (33.5%) respectively. Nearly all the participants (99.5%) had attained a form of formal education. More than 94% of the women had either a secondary or tertiary level of education. Primiparity was recorded in 34.0%, Multiparous women were 60.2%, while grand multiparous women made up 4.2% of the participants. (Table 1)

Table 1. Sociodemographic characteristics of participants

Variable	No (382)	%
Age		
20	24	6.3
21-30	228	59.3
31-40	124	32.4
≥41	6	1.6
Religion		
Christians	342	89.5
Moslems	14	3.7
Others	26	6.8
Tribe		
Ika	170	44.5
Ibo	84	22.0
Other	128	33.5
Education		
None	2	0.5
Primary	20	5.2
Secondary	218	57.1
Tertiary	142	37.2
Parity		
Primipara	130	34.0
Multipara	236	60.2
Grandmultipara	16	4.2

Table 2. Sociodemographic characteristics, obstetrics, and maternal health services use history and experience during the last childbirth

Variable	No Abuse (290)	Abused (92)	P Value
Age (Years)			
20	19	5	0.512
21-30	170	58	
31-40	95	29	
≥41	6	0	
Religion			
Christians	253	89	0.025
Moslems	14	0	
Others	23	3	
Tribe			
Ika	137	33	0.159
Ibo	61	23	
Others	92	36	
Education			
None	2	0	0.394
Primary	16	2	
Secondary	164	54	
Tertiary	106	36	
Parity			
Primipara	95	35	0.631
Multipara	183	53	
Grandmultipara	12	4	
ANC Use			
Yes	284	86	0.033
No	6	6	
Number of ANC attended			
≤3	109	23	0.027
≥4	181	69	
Place of Birth			
CHA	234	68	0.164
Others	56	24	
Number of Health workers at birth			
2	64	22	0.712
≥3	226	70	
Time of Delivery			
Day	216	52	0.001
Night	74	40	

ANC -Antenatal clinic; CHA -Central Hospital Agbor

Table 2 illustrates how sociodemographic factors, obstetric characteristics, and the history and experiences of maternal health services usage relate to DAA during the last childbirth. Significant factors linked to DAA during childbirth include identifying as a Christian ($p = 0.025$), not utilizing antenatal care ($p = 0.033$), having fewer antenatal care visits ($p = 0.027$), and giving birth at night ($p = 0.001$). The rate of Abuse in the study was 24.1%.

Figure 2. Bar chart for types of abuse suffered

The majority of the participants suffered multiple abuses, while non-dignified care and non-consented care were the next most common abuses suffered by the participants. Only 2 patients reported being detained after delivery for their inability to settle hospital bills.

Table 3. General satisfaction

Level of Satisfaction	Frequency	%
Very Dissatisfied	6	1.6
Dissatisfied	4	1.0
Neutral	46	12.0
Satisfied	44	11.5
Very satisfied	282	73.8

The satisfaction level among participants was high at 85.3%, with only 2.6% expressing dissatisfaction with their experiences during their most recent childbirth. Even though some women reported experiencing some form of abuse, many still felt satisfied with the overall childbirth process.

DISCUSSION

The study explores the experiences of newly delivered mothers regarding their experiences of abuse during the birthing process. From the survey, 24.1% of the participants reported one form of abuse or the other during the delivery. This is higher than the value of 19.7% reported by Oche *et al.*²⁴ in Sokoto and 18.3% by Mosenburg *et al.*²⁵ in Brazil. It is, however, lower than 47.6% from

Abakiliki reported by Nwafor *et al.*²¹ and 55.9% from Kano reported by Amole *et al.*²⁶ Higher values of 84.3%, 91.7%, and 98.0% have been reported by Nawab *et al.*²⁷ in India, Siraj *et al.* in Ethiopia, and Ugwu *et al.*²⁸ in South-East Nigeria. The wide variation in the prevalence of DAA among delivered mothers could be a result of multiple factors, with culture, beliefs, and societal roles of women contributing. Women's ability or willingness to report DAA will depend on their understanding of what constitutes abuse. In different cultural contexts, behaviors and practices during childbirth that are considered abusive or unacceptable in one culture might be seen as standard or even necessary in another.

Two studies from Guinea revealed that some women believe that pinching or slapping by healthcare providers is employed as a lifesaving measure for the woman or baby.^{29,30} These studies indicated that certain women perceive a medical rationale for slapping, believing it helps in the birthing process.^{29,30} Additionally, some participants in these studies viewed slapping as essential for disciplining women deemed disobedient. Likewise, a Nigerian study found that women believed providers were justified in slapping or pinching disobedient women to maintain discipline.³¹ In a survey conducted in Ethiopia, a substantial number of participants believed that it was justifiable for health professionals to yell at or shout at women. They considered this behavior acceptable as a means to save lives, prevent complications, or discipline women who were being disobedient.³⁰ The differing prevalence rates across different regions underscore the importance of standardisation of measurement tools to enable comparability across diverse groups.

The low prevalence of DAA in this study may be related to the centre's strong patient-centered care and regular training of labour ward nurses. There is a firm policy stating that providing patients with free antenatal care and delivery should not justify their mistreatment during childbirth. The

potential result is a high turnout for antenatal care at the center, with more than 200 patients registering each month and an annual average of over 1,000 deliveries.³²

The factors significantly associated with DAA during childbirth are identifying as a Christian ($p = 0.025$), not using antenatal care services ($p = 0.033$), having fewer antenatal care visits ($p = 0.027$), and delivering at night ($p = 0.001$).

Similar to the review by Amole *et al.*,²¹ Christian women significantly reported more cases of abuse than their Muslim counterparts. Oche *et al.*²⁴ and Siraj *et al.*³³ did not find any significant difference in the incidence of DAA between Christians and Muslims in their study. The emphasis on modesty and discouragement of showing women's bodies in the Islamic religion, combined with strong religious and cultural beliefs, may create a more supportive and positive environment during childbirth, especially when healthcare providers are culturally sensitive and respectful of these values and traditions. As a result, the likelihood of experiencing DAA may be reduced. The study found that Muslim women generally had lower levels of education, with many having no formal education or only primary education. In contrast, women in the Christian group were better educated. Women who attended secondary education or greater were more likely to report DAA.^{8,33} Higher education levels can empower women to advocate for themselves and insist on respectful treatment during delivery. Consequently, the potential for under-reporting of DAA among Muslim women cannot be dismissed, and further investigation capturing Muslim women with different levels of educational qualification will be needed to fully understand this variation. Educational qualification, however, did not independently affect the occurrence of DAA in this review.

Women who either skipped ANC or had fewer visits tended to report experiencing DAA during

childbirth. ANC offers crucial information about pregnancy, childbirth, and postpartum care. Women who do not regularly participate in such care may miss out on vital information, increasing their risk of receiving misinformation and facing mistreatment. Not attending ANC consistently can also prevent women from developing a relationship with their healthcare providers, leading to a lack of trust and comfort, which makes them more susceptible to disrespectful and abusive behavior. Additionally, women who infrequently attend ANC might often come from disadvantaged socioeconomic backgrounds; healthcare providers may harbor biases or stereotypes about such women, resulting in discriminatory and disrespectful treatment. Unfortunately, some healthcare providers might have negative perceptions of women who don't regularly attend ANC, seeing them as uncooperative or non-compliant. These attitudes can lead to disrespectful and abusive interactions, reinforcing a cycle of mistrust and poor health outcomes.

Women who gave birth at night experienced more mistreatment than those who delivered during the day. This finding aligns with the findings by Abya *et al.*³⁴ However, the review by Nawab *et al.*²⁸ did not find any notable differences between day and night deliveries. Multiple factors could contribute to this discrepancy, including insufficient staffing during nighttime, staff burnout and fatigue, limited resources available at night, and reduced supervision by authorities during nighttime hours.

In the group of women who experienced abuse, half (50%) said they endured multiple forms of mistreatment. This was followed by reports of non-dignified care at 5.8% and non-consented care at 3.7%. Earlier reviews^{8,20,21,228,34} identified non-dignified care, physical abuse, and non-consented care as the most common types of abuse. However, many of those studies did not

categorize women who experienced multiple forms of abuse.

The participants largely reported high satisfaction levels, with 85.3% falling into the satisfied or very satisfied categories, despite 24.1% having experienced some form of abuse. This suggests that the women prioritized the positive outcome of the delivery over the abuse faced during labour. Their joy from a successful delivery seemed to outweigh the negative experiences

Strengths and Limitations

This review is the first of its kind in this environment, it will therefore serve as a reference for future research in this area. Assessing DAA is inherently complex and challenging, with no objective method of evaluation; instead, self-reported incidents perceived as DAA were used as a basis for assessment. Any treatment perceived as unacceptable by a patient was considered a valid classification of DAA. The review focused on women who had given birth approximately six weeks prior, which raises the possibility of recall bias. Diverse personnel managed patients during labor, but the review did not examine how provider-related factors might contribute to DAA; this represents a potential area for future research. While the interviewers were not the same personnel involved in labour and delivery, the risk of social desirability bias cannot be discounted.

CONCLUSION

The review indicated that over 20% of women who give birth experience DAA, which can deter them from choosing facility-based deliveries. Providing respectful maternity care during childbirth is crucial not only for the woman and her unborn child but also for her family and the nation, as it promotes facility deliveries and the presence of skilled attendants, thereby lowering maternal mortality rates. Healthcare providers need ongoing training, retraining, and support to deliver respectful and responsible maternity care effectively.

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Authors contributions

MNR-Conception, design of the research and data acquisition

MNR and DP-Analysis, Data interpretation, Drafting the work, Review, final approval for publication, and both authors have agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

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